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Research Article

**ASSOCIATION BETWEEN SATRUCTURAL EMPOWERMENT
AND NURSES OUTCOMES AMONG THE PUBLIC HOSPITALS
OF LAHORE, PAKISTAN*****Amina Farooq¹, Maryam Rabbani², ³Razia Bano**^{1,2} Senior Lecturer, School of Nursing, Sharif Medical City Lahore, ³Acting Principal, School of Nursing, Sharif Medical City Lahore.**Abstract:**

Purpose: The purpose of the study was to determine the effect of Structural Empowerment on nursing outcome (Job Satisfaction). The aim of the study was to maintain an empowering work environment that enhances job satisfaction and nurses' retention and also for the better organizational outcome.

Method: A descriptive cross-sectional study was performed to determine the effect of empowering work environment on nursing outcome. A convenient sampling technique was used for the purpose to collect data from respondents. Job satisfaction was measured on Job Diagnostic Survey Questionnaire a five item Likert scale adapted from (Hackman & Oldham, 1975). Structural empowerment is measured on work effectiveness questionnaire adapted from (Lschinger, 2001).

Result: The main findings of the study are that Structural empowerment has a significance positive influence on nursing job satisfaction. In future broad study is recommended to explore the relationship between structural empowerment and job satisfaction further study is required to further elaborate the effect of work environment on nursing outcome.

Conclusion: The study concluded that mostly nurses are satisfied with their job due to empowered work environment. Those nurses who are working in empowered environment are satisfied with their job as compare to those nurses who are working in lack of empowered work environment. Structural empowerment is considering as one of the important factors for the nurse's job satisfaction their retention and better organizational outcome.

Key terms: work Environment, Structural Empowerment, and Job satisfaction.

Corresponding author:**Amina Farooq,**

Senior Lecturer, School of Nursing, Sharif Medical City Lahore.

*Email: aminafarooq470@gmail.com

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INTRODUCTION:

Nurses are the larger group of health care providers who provide seventy five percent care to the patient during hospitalization(Purdy et al., 2010). Job satisfaction is one of the major factors who play an important role in nurse's retention and organizational outcome. Similarly, environmental empowerment is the major source who provide the employees strength and motivation in their work and that includes decrease work load, developmental opportunities and assess to the participation in decision making.

Due to high levels of job dissatisfaction mostly staff nurses are leaving their jobs.Job dissatisfaction arises from workplace environment which includes increase workload, lack of developmental opportunities and lack of participation in decision making(Purdy et al., 2010).The work environment is the setting where nurses provide their care and facilities the patient (Laschinger et al., 2009). Nurses are facing difficulties and challenges in their working environment due to lack of organizational support and due to their poor working conditions. There is increasing demand for health care professional especially nurses due to increase population growth. In 2007 the shortage of nurses was eleven thousands and will be increased round about twenty two thousands in 2025.(Tomblin Murphy et al., 2009).By providing better working condition and empowered work environment the nursing outcome will be improve, in nursing outcome job satisfaction is an important factor because if the nurses are satisfied from their job their outcome would definitely improve and nurses will never leave their job(Purdy et al., 2010). The healthcare organizations needs to pay attention for decrease burnout of the nurses by providing them opportunity, give them courage, fulfill their needs and give them power(Purdy et al., 2010).

There are so many ways by which nurses can be retained but structural empowerment also one of the essential strategies. By providing structural empowerment the nurses can be satisfied from their job(Laschinger et al., 2009). Job satisfaction is a kind of pleasant and positive working state of employees which grow in the process of evaluating an employee's work experience. Structural empowerment is an important component for nursing job satisfaction(Chang et al., 2011). Structural empowerment is built upon the concept that removing conditions that raise dependence and powerlessness within an organization and will result in confident employee activities and enhanced performance (Manojlovich, 2007).

According to Kanter's theory (1993)there are some conditions required for empowerment which are formal and informal, Power and opportunity for advancement, access to information, access to support and access to resources(Laschinger et al., 2009). And these are the main factors for structural empowerment by providing these conditions to the employees they would be happy and satisfied from their job and by providing these conditions the job burnout could be decrease(Wagner et al., 2010).

Problem statement:

Nurses play a key role to ensure the patient care in health care settings. Doctors and other health care professionals are all depend on nurses to provide care to the patients. Patients and health care services are also reliant on the efficient nursing services at the hospitals. Nurses as a key source of health care services face the issues job satisfaction due to lack of attention of the administration. Structural empowerment is an important component for nurse's job satisfaction and their retention, many healthcare organizations did not provide structural empowerment to nurses which become the reason for the negative outcome. Moreover, the focus of the studies was not sufficient to resolve the issue among the nurses of the public hospital, so the solution of this problem can be presented.

Research Question:

What is the effect of structural empowerment on job satisfaction in nurses' work environment?

Objective of the study:

To determine the effect of Structural Empowerment on nursing outcome

Purpose of the study:

Purpose of the study was to determine the effect of Structural Empowerment on nursing outcome (Job Satisfaction).

Significance of the study:

The current study will be helpful to understand the issues of nurses' job satisfaction and the cause behind this. This research will provide the insight regarding the structural empowerment role in the nurse's job satisfaction. Likewise, administration of the hospitals can get the help from research and understand the relationship of structural empowerment and nurse's jobsatisfaction. It will also provide the support to the policy makers and management of the public and private hospital while assigning jobs and

empowerment as the key element which can influence the nurse's outcome.

Hypothesis:

Ho: There is no positive significant relationship between Structural empowerment and nurse's job satisfaction.

H1: There is positive significant relationship between Structural empowerment and nurse's job satisfaction.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

Workplace empowerment has become an important factor in determining nurse burnout, job satisfaction, and performance (Purdy et al., 2010). Nurses who are performing their job in empowered environment are highly satisfied and the percentage of their burnout is also decrease. Similarly, nurses who doing their job in non-empowered environment are leaving their job because of stress, workload and lack of decision making autonomy (Hauck et al., 2011). Nurses with decreased job satisfaction can lead to increase nursing turnover (Ning et al., 2009). Nurse's turnover is become very costly to health care organization due to selection of new employees, process of their training and maintaining of the staff shortage is one of the big issues. On average its cost one third of a new employee's annual salary to replace new employees. There is a need of healthcare administrators to take action and develop the strategies to retain the staff. Structural empowerment is important for nurse's job satisfaction (Wade et al., 2008). The effect of structural empowerment on the nursing work environment can contribute to job satisfaction (Walston, 2012).

Many Researches have showed the worldwide shortage of the nurses as they want to have autonomy in their profession, and their decision making at the unit level and also ensure reasonable workload, flexible schedule, and competitive pay and want to gain continuing education to stay on their current job (Walston, 2012).

Structural empowerment is a concept developed by Kanter (1993) Structural empowerment explains that when the organization provides opportunity and power through information, resources, and support then nurses are more effective and satisfied at the workplace (Purdy et al., 2010). The effect of structural empowerment on nurses' professional work environment can contribute to job satisfaction. Structural empowerment arises when the nurses have information, opportunity, support and resources to learn and grow (Stewart et al., 2010). Kanter's (1993) theory of structural empowerment is a frame work for this study and the result of this study which is the effect

of work environment on nursing outcomes may determine the impact of structural empowerment on nursing work environment and examine the influence of workplace empowerment on nurses' job satisfaction. Empowerment is main theme within nursing work environment and its impact on job satisfaction, nurses' retention, job strain and delivery of nursing care (Ning et al., 2009).

Kanter's theory shows a central theme to hospital managers to encourage and facilitate nurses to access resources, opportunities and information themselves (Walston, 2012). The structural empowerment theory explains that structural empowerment must be in place before it can be accessed by nurse leaders and then it can be directed through the employees, when nurses display greater empowerment there will be increase in job satisfaction (Stewart et al., 2010).

This theory helps to explain the importance of structural empowerment within the work environment and helps that how nursing work environment has a direct effect on the nurses' perception of job satisfaction. Therefore it is important to determine the effect of structural empowerment on the professional workplace environment and examine the effect of workplace empowerment on nurse job satisfaction; ignoring nurse job satisfaction will have negative outcome to health care administrators and nurse managers (Cortese et al., 2010). When nurses are unsatisfied from their job then nursing care will also compromise, so, the structural empowerment in nursing is a key component with nurse job satisfaction and affects the work performance (Walston, 2012).

METHODOLOGY:

Descriptive cross-sectional study design was used to collect the data from participants. The target population were the staff nurses of Jinnah hospital Lahore.

Sample size 171 was calculated through Slovenes formula and is selected through convenience sampling method. Job satisfaction was measured on Job Diagnostic Survey Questionnaire a five item Likert scale adapted from (Hackman & Oldham, 1975). Structural empowerment was measured on work effectiveness questionnaire adapted from (Lschinger, 2001). The questionnaire was consisted of fifteen questions eleven questions of structural empowerment and four of job satisfaction and responses ranged from 1 Strongly Disagree to 5 strongly Agree. Data was gathered by self-administered questionnaire.

Data was analysed through SPSS version 16.0 and descriptive statistics were used. Respondents were informed about the objectives of the study and their participation was voluntary and they were informed about their rights that you can withdraw any time from the study. Their privacy and confidentiality were assured. Duration for the study was from February to May 2016.

DATA ANALYSIS:

Descriptive and normality statistics

This chapter focuses on to data analysis. Main statistical procedures applied on data were discussed on this chapter and in this chapter after application of statistical procedures results are also discussed and hypotheses are tested at the end.

Demographic Characteristics:

Table: 1. Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

		Age	Gender	Marital Status	Experience
N	Valid	171	171	171	171
	Missing	0	0	0	0
Mean		2.09	1.94	1.51	2.36
Median		2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00
Mode		2	2	1 ^a	2
Std. Deviation		.667	.235	.513	.494
Sum		357	332	258	404

a. Multiple modes exist. The smallest value is shown

Table no:1 shows the demographic characteristics which were composed of four items Age, Gender, Marital Status, and Experience. Also Mean, Median, standard deviation and sum.

Age:

Table no: 2. Age distribution of participants

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	20-25	30	17.5	17.5	17.5
	25-35	97	56.7	56.7	74.3
	35-50	43	25.1	25.1	99.4
	Above 50	1	.6	.6	100.0
	Total	171	100.0	100.0	

Figure no: 1

Table no: 2 and figure no: 1 showed that data was collected from the Staff Nurses of different Age. Total respondents were 171 and the results regarding their age. The total respondents were of different age 30 were 20-25 years (17.5%), 97 were 25-35 years (56.7%), 43 were 35-50 years (25.1%) 1 was above 50 (.6%).

Gender:

Table no: 3. Gender distribution of participants

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	10	5.8	5.8	5.8
	Female	161	94.2	94.2	100.0
	Total	171	100.0	100.0	

Figure: 2

Table no: 3 and figure no: 2 showed that the data was gathered through 171 respondents. Mostly were females. 10 were Male (5.8%) and 161 were female (94.2%).

Marital status:**Table no :4. Marital Status of participants**

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Married	85	49.7	49.7	49.7
	Single	85	49.7	49.7	99.4
	Total	171	100.0	100.0	100.0

Figure: 3

Table no: 4 and figure no: 3 showed that the data was collected from 171 respondents in which include both married and singles. 85 were Married (49.7%) and 85 were single (49.7%).

Experience:**Table no: 5. Experience of participants**

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1-5Years	110	64.3	64.3	64.3
	6-10Years	60	35.1	35.1	99.4
	Above 10Years	1	.6	.6	100.0
	Total	171	100.0	100.0	

Figure: 4

Table no: 5 and figure no 4 shows the experience of the participants in their hospital. Based on their experience the participants shared their information about their working environment. 1- 5 years were 110 (64.3%), 6- 10 years were 60 (35.1%), above 10 years were 1 (.6%).

Skewness and Kurtosis:

Table no: 6. Summary of skewness and kurtosis results

	<i>Structural Empowerment</i>	<i>Job satisfaction</i>
Skewness	-.276	.558
S.E	.186	.186
Kurtosis	-.809	1.941
S.E	.369	.369

Normality tests:

Table no: 6 shows that first data was analyzed for missing values and other typing errors were also analyzed so that errors could rectify. Value of the data was assessed by analyzing normality. Normality was examined through skewness and kurtosis (Munro, 2005). scores of structural empowerment and job satisfaction were normally distributed and were well in range +1 to -1 more over both skewness and kurtosis were well in the range of +1.96 and -1.96 hence findings indicated normality of the data.

Descriptive Analysis:**Table no 7. Summary of Descriptive Analysis**

Variable	Range	S.D	Mean	Median
Structural Empowerment	52.00	1.10	37.46	39
Job satisfaction	39.00	4.96	14.72	16

Dependent variable:**Job satisfaction**

Table no: 7 shows that Summed scores were used to calculate means range, median and standard deviation with the purpose of conducting descriptive analysis of job satisfaction. Sample of 171 nurses was used for analysis purpose range of score was 39.00 as our mean and standard deviation are (M =14.72, SD =4.96).

Independent variable:**Structural Empowerment**

Table no: 7 shows that Summed scores were used to calculate means range, median and standard deviation with the purpose of conducting descriptive analysis of structural empowerment. Sample of 171 nurses was used for analysis purpose range of score was 52.00 as our mean and standard deviation are (M = 37.46, SD = 1.10). Laschinger et al. (2001) reported score 23-30 as high empowerment 14-22 as moderate level of perception about empowerment whereas 6-13 as lower level findings revealed high score which are between moderate to high.

Table no: 8. Summary of Reliability analysis

	Cronbach alpha
Structural empowerment	.875
Job satisfaction	.806

Validity and Reliability Assessment:

Table no: 8 shown that the value of Cronbach alpha for the structural empowerment is .875 which is above 0.7 is the acceptable indicator of internal consistency reliability. Similarly, the Cronbach alpha value for job satisfaction is .806 that is above 0.7 and meets the standard criteria so, the instrument of the study is reliable.

Table no: 9. Summary of KMO Bartlett's assumptions

	KMO	Bartlett's Test		
		Approx	Df	Sig
Job Satisfaction	.798	206.758	6	.000**
Structural Empowerment	.833	874.455	55	.000**

**p<0.01

Convergent validity:

Table no: 9 Shows that KMO value for job satisfaction is .798 which is above .50 and Bartlett's test is 0 which is less than 0.05 and significant and meet the standard criteria. Similarly, the KMO value for structural empowerment is .833 which is above than .50 and Bartlett's test is 0 and significant. So, the whole set criteria are fulfilled, and instrument of the study is valid.

Regression analysis:

Regression analysis was conducted to examine the relationship between variables. To examine the direct effects of structural empowerment on dependent variables job satisfaction linear regressions was used to examine the hypothesized relationships. Value of r square was used to explain the amount of variance same thing is explained by adjusted r square but in a more accurate way.

Structural Empowerment - outcomes relationships:**Regression analysis for Structural empowerment with job satisfaction****Table no: 10. Results of the Main Effect Hypotheses**

	<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	β	<i>P</i>
Constant	5.468	1.123		
Structural empowerment	.247	.029	.551	.000
R ² =.304				
ΔR^2 .304				

Table no: 10 shown that the Results revealed the Structural empowerment significantly predicted job satisfaction. With beta value .551 (p=.000) showing significant positive relationship between or structural empowerment and job satisfaction. Whereas value of ΔR^2 showing 30 % (F=73.869, p < .001) of variance contributed by independent variable (structural empowerment) in dependent variable (job satisfaction). So, the model is fit.

DISCUSSION:

The purpose of current study was to determine the effect of structural empowerment on the nurse's job satisfaction. The results support the hypothesis and explain the relationship between structural empowerment and nurse's outcome. The current study supports the view that the structural empowerment plays an important role in nurse's job satisfaction and their retention in organization. Study highlights the importance that the nurses are large group of people in healthcare setting who provide maximum care to the patient during hospitalization. Due to high levels of job dissatisfaction mostly staff nurses are leaving their jobs. Job dissatisfaction arises from their workplace environment in which includes heavy workload, lack of development opportunities and lack of participation in decision making (Purdy et al., 2010). There are so

many ways by which nurses can be retained but structural empowerment also one of the strategy by providing structural empowerment the nurses can be satisfied from their job (Laschinger et al., 2009). The result of this study also reveals that structural empowerment has a significant positive influencing on job satisfaction.

Data was collected from the Staff Nurses of different Age. Total respondents were 171. In which 17.5% were 20-25 years, 56.7% were 25-35 years, and 25.1% were 35-50 years and .6% was above 50 years. Participants were both male and female the percentage of gender, 5.8% Male and 94.2% female. The study participants were both married and single 49.7% were married and 49.7% were single. The participants were falls in different years of experience, 64.3%

experience was 1-5 years, 35.1% experience was 6-10 years, and .6% experience was above 10 years. Result of simple regression analysis revealed the Structural empowerment significantly predicted job satisfaction. With beta value .551 ($p=.000$) showing significant positive relationship between structural empowerment and job satisfaction. Whereas value of ΔR^2 showing 30 % ($F=73.869$, $p <.001$) of variance contributed by independent variable (structural empowerment) in dependent variable (job satisfaction). Regression analysis shows that structural empowerment has significance positive influencing on job satisfaction.

Current study reveals that with the help of structural empowerment we can achieve the nurse's job satisfaction and the better organizational outcome. So, with the help of these findings organization should develop different attitude in order to overcome these issues. Diminished work load access to the better opportunities and participation in decision making are provided to the employees to get their efficient nursing outcome.

CONCLUSION:

Current study examines the relationship between structural empowerment and nurse's outcome. Study results shown that there exist the positive and significant relationship between structural empowerment and nurse's job satisfaction. Similarly, the results of (Purdy et al., 2011) show the positive and significant relationship between structural empowerment and nurse's outcome. Therefore, the health care organization should emphasize the structural empowerment to attain the better nurse's outcome such nurses outcome will become the reason of overall health care efficiency as well.

LIMITATION:

The current study was conducted in a very short time. Due to shortage of time convenient sampling technique was used for the purpose of collection of data from respondents. The study is descriptive cross sectional and data was collected from only one hospital.

RECOMMENDATION:

1. In future broad study is recommended to explore the relationship between structural empowerment and job satisfaction.
2. In addition, studies should focus on the other factors which may influence nurse's job satisfaction and burnout.

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